

Glutathione : Synthesis, Mechanism and its Complexing Properties

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The fundamental developments in the field of metal complexes of glutathione, dealing with various physico-chemical aspects alongwith their structural behaviour have been discussed, covering the period 1917-1992. Analytical data have also been incorporated in some cases. The importance of glutathione as anticancer reagent, its biochemical properties and wide applications have been discussed.

Most of the recent developments in the coordination chemistry are based on the complexation reaction of the metal ion with various ligands. Metal complexes of glutathione (GSH) serve important functions in our biological system and play a dominant role in protein metabolism. They are important constituents of enzymes, proteins and are present in many parts of the biological systems¹. Zinc complex is present in a number of enzymes and a protein containing cadmium bound to SH groups has been isolated from horse kidneys¹. The study of metal peptide interactions is of biological interest since it provides a simple model to elucidate the binding sites and the nature of linkages involved in metal-ligand binding.

Glutathione (reduced), a biological reducing agent in thiol dependent enzyme reactions, has recently been reported to have anticancer activity². Novi³ administered reduced glutathione to rats bearing aflatoxin B₁ induced liver tumors caused regression of tumor growth and resulted in survival of the animals. Since glutathione is a harmless natural product, it merits further investigation as a potential antitumor drug for humans.

In view of the dominant role of glutathione and its metal complexes in various biochemical systems, the review reflects our critical selection of fundamental developments in this field. The present review covers the fundamental developments in the field of metal-complexes of glutathione dealing with physicochemical studies and structural behaviour during the period 1917-1992. Although, we are not able to provide extensive coverage of developments in broad areas, such as

chromatography, thermal analysis etc., we have tried to include major review articles and chapters relevant to the topic under study.

Occurrence : Waelsch⁴ collected data concerning the occurrence of GSH, showing among others, liver (170 mg %), spleen (100 mg %) and yeast (130 mg %) to be the main sources.

Structure : Glutathione is composed of glutamic acid, cysteine and glycine.

γ -glutamylcysteinylglycine (glutathione)

The exact formula of this tripeptide was suggested in 1929 by Pirie and Pinhey⁵ using physicochemical methods and found four different pK values, which they correlated with a SH, a NH₃⁺ and two COOH groups. The structure also suggested by Hopkins⁶ and by Kendall *et al.*⁷ using methods of degradation, was established in 1935 through a synthesis carried out by Harington and Mead⁸.

The cysteine imparts to glutathione an SH group and so glutathione is found in two forms, viz. reduced (1) and oxidised (2) glutathione.

Properties Glutathione is a colourless crystalline compound soluble in water, f.w. 307.77, m.p. 195°, $[\alpha]_D^{17} - 21.0^\circ$ ⁸, -18.5° ⁶, -16.0° ¹⁰, -17.4° ¹²; aqueous solution of the disulphide, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 108^\circ$, isoelectric point $p_I = 2.83$. Glutathione may be involved in oxidation of elemental sulphur. The linear polysulphide so obtained as oxidised to sulphite or thiosulphate.

Synthesis of GSH and similar peptides : The five methods for synthesis of GSH are the routes followed by Harington and Mead⁸, du Vigneaud and Miller⁹, Hegedues¹⁰, Rudinger and Sorm¹¹ and Goldschmidt and Jutz¹². Besides GSH, the following similar peptides have been prepared : α -L-glutamyl-L-cysteinylglycine (iso-GSH)¹³, γ -D-glutamyl-L-cysteinylglycine¹⁴ and β -L-aspartyl-L-cysteinylglycine (asparthione)¹⁵ They all show considerable activity in the glyoxalase test^{15,16}.

Biochemical mechanisms : From the time of its discovery, glutathione (GSH) has been considered for playing an important role in cellular hydrogen and electron transport^{17,18}. This possibility was suggested by the ease of interconversion of the sulphhydryl and

disulphide forms of the compound (equation 1) in the presence of suitable tissue preparations,

It appeared that tissues could reduce GSSG, and that the GSH so formed was readily oxidised by molecular O₂. Hopkins and Elliott¹⁹ estimated that the oxidation of GSH in the presence of liver mice proceeded at a rate of about 40 dm³ of O₂ per g tissue per h.

Enzymatic reduction of GSSG : Mann²⁰ reported that GSSG is reduced by a mixture of glucose and a heat labile protein fraction. At the same time, Meldrum reported that intact mammalian erythrocytes reduced GSSG in the presence of glucose. The reduction of GSSG by extracts of lens tissue was reported by Hermann and Moses²¹.

Biosynthesis of glutathione : Of the various compounds used as models for the investigation of enzymatic peptide synthesis, glutathione (GSH) is of particular interest. The enzymes which catalyse the formation of GSH have been found in the livers of pigeons^{22,23} as well as of various mammals²⁴. The presence of the GSH synthesising system in extracts of *E. coli* was demonstrated by Samuels²⁵. The tripeptide is formed in two steps catalysed by ATP requiring reactions. The first step is the condensation of γ -glutamate with cysteine :

The second step is the condensation of the dipeptide with glycine :

Active transport system (γ -glutamyl cycle) . In this system, some of the GSH is transported out of the cell, in the extra-cellular space. It is converted by membrane bound γ -glutamyltransferase to Cys-Gly and γ -glutamylamino acids. The products so formed are trans-

ported back into the cell and are cleaved from Cys-Gly to Gly and Cys, and γ -glutamylamino acid to 5-oxoproline and the amino acid. 5-Oxoproline is converted to glutamic acid so that γ -glutamyl cycle can repeat. Glutathione also participates in the transport of amino acids. A membrane-bound enzyme, γ -glutamyl-transpeptidase, catalyses the transfer of the γ -glutamyl group of glutathione to the α -amino group of an acceptor amino acid.

Enzymes of glutathione :

Glutathione S-transferase : Glutathione S-transferase is a group of enzymes of the liver cytosol which catalyses reaction of glutathione (acting as a nucleophile) with a wide range of electrophilic substances,

where, GSH is reduced glutathione, R may be an aliphatic, aromatic or heterocyclic radical and X may be a sulphate, nitrite, halide, epoxy or ethene group, or the cyanide group of a thiocyanate.

Glutathione peroxidase : Glutathione peroxidase protects cells against the destructive effects of hydrogen peroxide. Glutathione peroxidase also protects against the formation of met-hemoglobin by consuming hydrogen peroxide in the reaction,

Reduced	Oxidised
glutathione	glutathione

The active site of glutathione peroxidase contains a residue of the unusual amino acid selenocysteine, in which the sulphur atom of cysteine is replaced by a selenium atom. The SH group of this residue has advantageous properties in the mechanism of this and other selenium enzymes.

Mechanism : The selenolate ($E-Se^-$) form of residue reduces the peroxide substrate to an alcohol and is in turn oxidised to selenenic acid ($E-SeOH$). Glutathione now comes into action by forming a selenosulphide adduct ($E-Se-S-G$). A second glutathione then regenerates the active form of the enzyme by attacking the selenosulphide to form oxidised glutathione (Fig. 1).

Glutathione reductase : Glutathione reductase has been demonstrated in pea seeds by Mapson and Goddard^{26,27}, in wheat germ by Conn and Vennes-

land^{28,29} and in animal tissues and yeast by Rall and Lehninger³⁰. The reaction catalysed is shown in equation (4).

Fig. 1 Proposed catalytic mechanism of glutathione peroxidase

Review of literature

In this section, an attempt has been made to compile the available literature on the topic under review

Quantitative . The quantitative study of metal-complex formation by glutathione (H_3L) presents difficulties because of the multiplicity of sites at which binding of the metal ion is possible.

These comprise the thiol group, the two carboxyl, the amino group and the two peptide linkages.

Kozłowski³¹ studied crystalline copper compound of oxidised yeast glutathione and also studied copper compound of oxidised glutathione of yeast. Pire³² studied crystallography of glutathione. Eisenbrand and Wegel³³ studied the compounds of zinc with glycine, cysteine and glutathione and the nature of the bond of insulin and zinc. Zegzhda *et al.*³⁴ studied compounds of silver with glutathione. Murakami *et al.*³⁵ studied glutathione ferrous salt.

Grassetti *et al.*³⁶ made investigations on quantitative analytical determination of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate and glutathione. Suke *et al.*³⁷ determined glutathione crystals of b-form.

Bayer *et al.*³⁸ made investigations on transition metal complexes of thiol compounds. Neville and Drakenberg³⁹ studied mercuric mercury and methyl-

mercury complexes of glutathione. Hoda *et al.*⁴⁰ reported glutathione copper salt. Verma *et al.*⁴¹ studied milligram amount of thiol groups with ferricyanide by using 2,6-dichlorophenolindophenol as titrant. Gowda and Mahadevappa⁴² estimated metal complexes of cysteine and glutathione with chloramine-T and dichloramine-T Takashio⁴³ prepared glutathione from its cuprous mercaptide. Hayakawa⁴⁴ made study on glutathione zinc complex. Tarui *et al.*⁴⁵ studied the precipitation of glutathione copper salt. Marzotto⁴⁶ prepared dioxouranium(VI) complexes of the tripeptide glutathione. The results indicate that coordination occurred at the carboxylate groups, acting as monodentate ligands, whereas no significant interaction with the amino and sulphhydryl groups takes place. Zegzhda *et al.*^{47,48} studied Pd^{II} and Ag^I complexes with cysteine and glutathione. They found the acid dissociation constants values of the ligand (H₃L) as $pK_1 = 3.30$, $pK_2 = 8.60$ and $pK_3 = 9.95$. The complex [Pd(NH₃)₂(H₂L)]₂ PdCl₄ was isolated. Abello *et al.*⁴⁹ investigated the complexing behaviour of Co^{II} with reduced glutathione, oxidised glutathione and glycylmethionine. Goda *et al.*⁵⁰ studied the structures of oxovanadium(IV)-glutathione complexes and reductive complex formation between glutathione and vanadate(+5). They observed three types of GSH-oxovanadium(IV) complexes at pH 4–10; at pH 5, these were unstable. Rabenstein⁵¹ studied metal complexes of glutathione and their biological significance. Shanthi *et al.*⁵² reported Cr^{III} complexes of amino acids with anion of glutathione or nicotinic acid as a co-ligand. Mukherjee *et al.*⁵³ made investigation on complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} with glutathione. The results indicate that all the complexes precipitated between pH 4–6, are octahedral.

Qualitative : Kendall and Nord⁵⁴ studied reversible oxidation-reduction systems of cysteine-cysteine and reduced and oxidised glutathione. Pasquier *et al.*⁵⁵ studied combinations of copper with glutathione. Livermore and Muecke⁵⁶ determined formation of a mixed disulphide of cysteine and glutathione. Benesch *et al.*⁵⁷ investigated the reactivity of the sulphhydryl group in glutathione and related peptides. Dubnoff⁵⁸ reported cobalamine glutathione complex. Rost and Raport⁵⁹ studied redox potential of glutathione. Benesch and Benesch⁶⁰ studied the acid strength of the SH group in cysteine and related compounds. Perrin

and Watt⁶¹ studied complex formation of Zn and Cd with glutathione. They proposed several possible structures for the complexes ML⁻ and ML₂⁴⁻ involving coordination to one or more of the following sites in the glutathione anion : an oxygen atom of the glutamyl residue (A), the amino nitrogen (B), the peptide oxygen (C) or nitrogen (D), the sulphur atom (E), the second peptide oxygen (F) or nitrogen (G), and an oxygen atom of the glycyl carboxyl group (H). They suggested a model for zinc complex in which the metal is bonded through the sites A, B, D and E.

ZnL⁻ is postulated to have the structure (I) (Fig. 2). Bonding of the zinc to the glutamyl portion in (I) is similar to that due to the amino and carboxyl groups in the 1 : 1 zinc-penicillamine complex (II), but the sulphur-nitrogen chelate ring in (I) should be less stable than its counter part in (II), linkage through a peptide nitrogen being weaker than through a primary amino group.

Fig. 2.

Martin and Edsall⁶² investigated the association of divalent cations with glutathione, and they concluded that γ -glutamyl residue may function as a relatively strong point of attachment for certain metal ions, thus permitting the sulphur atom to remain relatively free and hence active.

Mairesse-Ducarmois *et al.*⁶³ studied coulometric determination of thiols and disulphides using electrogenerated Hg^{II}. Kuznetsev and Shumakovich⁶⁴ studied electrosynthesis of the catalytic cobalt-glutathione complex. Srivastava⁶⁵ performed biamperometric titration of sulphhydryl groups at low concentrations using mercury pool electrodes. Gowda and Mahadevappa⁶⁶ estimated metal complexes of cysteine with the zinc group of metals and glutathione complexes of Ag, Hg and Cd with chloramine-T and dichloramine-T. Verma *et al.*⁶⁷ determined glutathione with bromine chloride in acidic

fied solutions of potassium iodide and starch. Jezowska-Trzebiatowska *et al.*⁶⁸ studied metal-glutathione interaction in aqueous solution and Pd^{II} complexes with glutathione.

Sakanc *et al.*⁶⁹ studied electrochemical behaviour of glutathione (oxidised form) on a mercury electrode. GSSG yielded 1-3 reduction peaks on cyclic voltammograms with increasing concentration of GSSG. Xu *et al.*⁷⁰ made potentiometric and spectrophotometric studies on the complexation of *cis*-diamminediaquoplatinum(II) ion with cysteine, methionine and glutathione. Motonaka *et al.*⁷¹ studied potentiometric titrations of *N*-acetyl-L-cysteine, glutathione and D-penicillamine with an iodide-selective electrode.

Holloway and Battersby⁷² made simultaneous analysis of glutathione in reduced and oxidised forms by capillary iso-tachopheresis and observed that reduced glutathione are best stored in acidic medium (pH 3-4) in a frozen state.

Gowda *et al.*⁷³ made oxidimetric determination of amino acids and their metal complexes with organic monochloroamines. Katz⁷⁴ studied chemically modified electrode with related activity for sulphhydryl compounds. Inagaki and Reddijk⁷⁵ reported reactions of chloro(diethylenetriamine)platinum(I) chloride with glutathione, oxidised glutathione and *S*-methylglutathione leading to the formation of an *S*-bridged dinuclear unit. Kapoor *et al.*⁷⁶ studied the reaction of glutathione with Hg^{II} at various pH values by alkalimetric titration. Katz and Solovev⁷⁷ studied chemically modified electrodes with affinity to sulphhydryl compounds.

Odenheimer and Wolf⁷⁸ reported reactions of *cis*-platin with sulphur containing amino acids and peptides, cysteine and glutathione. In the reaction, the molecule of glutathione acts as a bidentate chelating ligand, coordinating to the platinum via the cysteinyl sulphur and nitrogen atom (the later forming part of the peptide bond to glutamic acid) forming a five-membered ring (Fig. 3).

Jovanovic *et al.*⁷⁹ studied the reaction of glutathione with molybdenum(VI). Korsunskii *et al.*⁸⁰ reported reaction of a thiolate complex of oxycobalamin with reduced glutathione in alkaline medium. Javanovic and Stankovic⁸¹ studied on silver electrode direct potentiometric determination of glutathione with copper(II). JICS-2

Arikawa and Huber⁸² studied amperometry of thiols in a flow injection system with a nickel oxide electrode.

Fig. 3. Interaction of *cis*-platin with glutathione.

Kinetic and equilibrium of the reaction of some thiolate ions with trinitro-aromatic compounds and intrinsic reactivities have been studied by Crampton and Stevens⁸³. Shoukry⁸⁴ reported complex formation equilibria between Hg^{II} complexes of pencillamine and glutathione and transition metal ions. Subramaniam and Narayanan⁸⁵ reported polarographic behaviour of V^{IV}-glutathione system at DME using acetic acid-acetate buffer and sodium perchlorate as the background electrolyte. Tiwari and Verma⁸⁶ performed titrimetric microdetermination of some sulphur-containing amino acids. Forbes and Hamlin⁸⁷ used organomercuric reagents for determining GSH by visual or amperometric titration method. They concluded that mercuric chloride method for determining GSH is rapid, simple and accurate.

Spectroscopy : ESR of monomer-dimer equilibriums involving Mo^V complexes with cysteine and glutathione has been studied by Huang and Haight⁸⁸.

Malhotra *et al.*⁸⁹ reported a new scheme on kinetics of Ni^{II}-γ-L-glutamyl-L-cysteinylglycine. Schilling⁹⁰ investigated glutathione hydrolysis and chromatographic separation of the reaction products. Kato *et al.*⁹¹ studied effects of trace elements on the stability and stabilisation of glutathione. Jones *et al.*⁹² reported evidence for the generation of hydroxyl radicals from a Cr^V intermediate isolated from the reaction of chromate with glutathione. Sofic *et al.*⁹³ determined glutathione, glutathione disulphide, ascorbic acid and dehydroascorbic acid in tissues by reversed-phase liquid chromatography with electrochemical detection. Pacz *et al.*⁹⁴ studied electro-oxidation of glutathione on graphite electrodes modified with preadsorbed vita-

min B₁₂ and preadsorbed cobalamin phthalocyanines.

Zenin⁹⁵ studied NMR of the conformational state of glutathione in water. Corrie and Williams⁹⁶ made investigation on thermodynamic considerations in coordination. Kertesz and Wolf⁹⁷ studied ESR of glutathione on conformational aspects. Tiezzi⁹⁸ determined association between Mn^{II} and peptides by using NMR and EPR spectroscopy. Fuhr and Rabenstein⁹⁹ investigated NMR of the solution chemistry of metal complexes to find out the nature of binding of Cd, Zn, Pb and Hg by glutathione. Rabenstein¹⁰⁰ studied NMR of the acid base chemistry of amino acids and peptides. Jung *et al.*¹⁰¹ investigated on carbon-13 NMR on the dissociation equilibriums of aminothiols compounds. Mitchell and Scarle¹⁰² reported thiolato complexes of Mo^V and Mo^{III} by electron paramagnetic resonance.

Jezowska-Trzebiatowska¹⁰³ reported NMR and EPR of Cu^{II}-glutathione interaction in water solution. The results suggest that the peptide linkage between cysteine and the glutamic acid reacts first. Since the Cu^{II} ion promotes the deprotonation of the peptide linkage in basic medium, it would be expected that the deprotonated nitrogen atom will be bonded to the metal ion. The sulphur atom combines with the same metal ion, forming the five-membered ring (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4.

Antonow *et al.*¹⁰⁴ studied Mössbauer spectroscopy of adenine guanine and glutathione iron complexes. Jezowska-Trzebiatowska¹⁰⁵ investigated metal-glutathione interaction in aqueous solution. Delfini *et al.*¹⁰⁶ reported NMR of the oxovanadium(IV)-(glutathione)₂ complex. Raman spectroscopy of the interactions of metallic ions with molecules of biological

interest has been reported by Alex and Saroie¹⁰⁷. They also studied vibrational of the complexation of methylmercury by glutathione¹⁰⁸. The results show that the favoured step in the complexation of these species is through the substitution of the proton on the thiol group of GSH by a CH₃Hg⁺ ion. Podonyi and Reid¹⁰⁹ studied NMR of the conformations of free and lanthanide-complexed glutathione in aqueous solution. They suggested that the complexation sites of the glutathione molecule are the two carboxylate end-groups only.

Kitagawa *et al.*¹¹⁰ reported EPR on the interaction of hexavalent chromium with glutathione or cysteine leading to the production of pentavalent chromium and its stability. Shoukry *et al.*¹¹¹ studied polarimetric and NMR of the complexation of mercury by thiols. The results indicate that a binding is sufficiently strong that a significant fraction of Hg^{II} is present as Hg (glutathione)₃ under physiol-conditions. Cheesman *et al.*¹¹² reported NMR of the solution chemistry of metal complexes. Shi and Dalal¹¹³ investigated the mechanism of the chromate reduction by glutathione leading to ESR evidence for the glutathionyl radical and an isolable chromium(V) intermediate. The results provide a new mechanism for the reduction of chromate by GSH *in vitro* cellular environment and help to understand the increase in Cr^{VI}-induced DNA strand breaks at elevated GSH levels. Appleton *et al.*¹¹⁴ reported NMR of the reactions of the *cis*-diaminodiaquoplatinum(II) cation with glutathione and amino acids containing a thiol group. Kadima and Rabenstein¹¹⁵ studied NMR of the solution chemistry of metal complexes.

Biological studies : Racker¹¹⁶ studied glutathione as a coenzyme in intermediary metabolism. Karl Myrback and Willstaedt¹¹⁷ reported inhibition of Ag⁺ and the complexing of Ag⁺ by certain sulphur-containing compounds.

Lawrence¹¹⁸ reported induction of erythrocyte reduced glutathione instability by dilution of normal blood. Blood preservatives for the glutathione stability test has been reported by Mathai and Beuther¹¹⁹. Glutathione instability in normal blood has been reported by Des-Forges¹²⁰. Rony *et al.*¹²¹ studied oxidation of glutathione by serum. Kosmider¹²² reported blood glutathione level in experimental poisoning with metallic mercury. Hamed *et al.*¹²³ reported the complexation between enterobactin and glutathione for iron. Abe *et*

*al.*¹²⁴ determined removal of substances inhibiting glutathione leading to copper salt formation. Tanno *et al.*¹²⁵ studied indium-113m-labelled glutathione as a brain-scanning and blood pool scanning agent. Srivastava *et al.*¹²⁶ studied agents for glutathione metabolism in erythrocytes, organic hydroperoxides. Gutovskaya *et al.*¹²⁷ reported the effect of a chelate compound of copper with glutathione on some biochemical blood indexes of experimental animals. Vortisch *et al.*¹²⁸ developed model on the coordination of copper in enzymes, structure and stability of cuprous complexes with sulphur-containing ligands. Sugiura¹²⁹ reported electronic properties of sulphhydryl and imidazole containing peptide-Co^{II} complexes showing their relationship to Co^{II}-substituted 'blue' copper proteins.

Mefford and Adams¹³⁰ reported reduced glutathione in guinea pig and rat tissues by hplc. Jackson *et al.*¹³¹ studied metal-ligand complexes involved in rheumatoid arthritis. Ercan *et al.*¹³² studied ^{99m}Tc-glutathione — the labelling and distribution in rats. Mecheloni *et al.*¹³³ determined metal-ligand complexes involved in rheumatoid arthritis. Fritzberg *et al.*¹³⁴ studied ^{99m}Tc-glutathione and role of reducing agent on renal retention. Tipping *et al.*¹³⁵ reported the interactions of triethyltin with rat glutathione-S-transferases A, B and C. Chata *et al.*¹³⁶ investigated chemical nature of a methylmercury complex in the liver cytosol of rats exposed to methylmercury chloride. Jezowska-Trzebiatowska and Wolowies¹³⁷ studied Pd^{II} complex with cystidine-guanosine pair in DMSO. Rabenstein *et al.*¹³⁸ studied glutathione in intact and hemolysed erythrocytes by proton magnetic resonance spectroscopy.

Mirabell *et al.*¹³⁹ found out correlation of the *in vitro* cytotoxic and *in vivo* antitumour activities of gold(I) coordination complexes. Czuderna and Rochalska¹⁴⁰ determined the interaction between zinc, cobalt, iron and mercury in mice by instrumental neutron activation analysis. Nuncz-Vergara and Scuell¹⁴¹ investigated biochemical approach to the role of glutathione in strong ethanol ingestion. Alexander *et al.*¹⁴² studied excretion of lead in rat bile — the role of glutathione. Balthrop *et al.*¹⁴³ reported the binding of methylmercury and methylmercury-thiol complexes by myelin isolated from mice of differing selenium status. Mason *et al.*¹⁴⁴ studied tying glutathione in knots. Katano *et al.*¹⁴⁵ reported antioxidant compositions con-

taining vitamin E and glutathione for cosmetics.

General : Theodor¹⁴⁶ studied chemistry and properties of glutathione. Racker¹⁴⁷ reported glutathione as a coenzyme in intermediary metabolism.

Laufer *et al.*¹⁴⁸, Muraki and Mizoguchi¹⁴⁹ studied on glutathione. Mannervik *et al.*¹⁵⁰ and Meister^{151,152} reviewed a brief history of glutathione including its discovery and survey of its metabolism and functions

Application

Glutathione is used as an anticancer reagent. It serves as a sulphhydryl buffer and amino acid transporter across the cell membrane. It protects red cell from oxidative damage. Glutathione (reduced) is essential for maintaining the normal structure of red blood cells and for keeping haemoglobin in the ferrous state. It is actively participated in the group translocation mechanism. It serves as a biological redox agent, as a coenzyme and cofactor and as a substrate in certain coupling reactions catalysed by glutathione-S-transferase. Glutathione also plays a role as a reduced carrier for the reduction of glutaredoxin which like thioredoxin, is a hydrogen donor for nucleotide reductase and for the reduction of the carrier-bound sulphate reduction pathway of *E. coli*. One important role of glutathione is to maintain the enzymes in the active reduced form. The most important metabolic function of glutathione (GSH) is to keep cysteine-thiols on proteins reduced by virtue of the following reactions

A proposed hypothesis about the biological role of GSH in the working mechanism of platinum anticancer drugs states that GSH can act as an inactivator of platinum complexes, thereby preventing binding to DNA and also that GSH can act as a tripping agent of DNA-Pt mono-adducts thereby preventing further reaction to form the cytotoxic bifunctional adducts. This makes a binding study of platinum compounds with GSH highly relevant

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